

COMPARATIVE ASSESSMENT OF CYTOKINE STATUS IN ANGINA PECTORIS

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Annotation. World wide, mortality from cardiovascular diseases (CVD) is in the first place and accounts for ~60% in the structure of total mortality [3].

The science of cardiology is engaged in the study of new markers of coronary heart disease (CHD), which were aimed at risk stratification and diagnosis in patients with acute coronary syndrome (ACS). It is known that ACS is based on vascular aseptic inflammation, which contributes to the progression of the atherosclerotic process from the stage of formation of atherosclerotic plaque (AB) to the development of destructive changes and thrombosis in the lumen of the coronary artery. At the same time, the degree of activity of vascular inflammation is the most important characteristic of destructive changes in AB. In this regard, the identification of factors that would reflect the degree of inflammation activity and directly determine the prognosis of the outcome of ACS is a purposeful work to find and study new markers of ACS [4,5].

Keys words: angina pectoris, cytokines, distribution, clinic

Inflammation of the vascular wall attracts circulating leukocytes, which is facilitated by increased expression of adhesion molecules and cytokines. In conditions of inflammation, endothelial activation of inflammatory mediators such as IL-6, IL-1, TNF, CRP is observed, which, in turn, enhance endothelial dysfunction, closing a vicious circle [1].

In chronic diseases, TNF is also able to induce insulin resistance and dyslipidemia. An increase in the stiffness of the arterial bed leads to a violation of the damping function of the arteries, negatively affects hemodynamics and contributes to the development of left ventricular myocardial hypertrophy, its diastolic dysfunction [2]. The aim of this study was to study the cytokine status in atypical angina pectoris (AS).

Materials and methods: 41 patients, 21 men, 20 women, aged 40-70 years, with atypical angina pectoris were included in the study. The average age is 56 ± 4.5 years. All patients underwent a comprehensive examination provided for by the standards of medical care for ACS. In the blood plasma of patients, determine IL-1 β , IL-6, IL-10 and TNF- α . Blood sampling was performed at the time of admission of the patient, before verification of the diagnosis, in an amount of 5 ml by venipuncture.

The control group consisted of 20 practically healthy individuals, comparable in age and gender. The comparison group included 40 patients with arterial hypertension and coronary artery disease with typical angina pectoris. Statistical processing of the material was performed using the Russified package "Statistics 8.0". For continuous values, the average values (M) and standard deviations (SD) were calculated. The reliability of differences in quantitative features was assessed using the Student's t-test (with parametric distribution) and the Mann-Whitney U-test (with nonparametric distribution).

Results of 40 patients of the comparison group - patients with arterial hypertension, chronic coronary heart disease. The diagnosis was verified according to accepted standards; dispensary observation and outpatient treatment were performed. The control group is -20 people, practically healthy people according to the results of the medical examination.

Discussion: Clinically, chest pain was noted in patients with atypical angina pectoris without a clear connection with provoking factors. Often the pain is described as at rest, starting from a low level of intensity, which gradually increases, persists for 15 minutes, and then its intensity slowly decreases.

With typical angina pectoris, there is a pain syndrome by localization and characteristics of typical angina pectoris, which is noted during physical exertion, and stops some time after exertion or stops after taking nitrates.

Cytokines in the comparison groups showed characteristic shifts depending on comorbidity. In a study in patients with AS, a 2- and 3-fold increase in the level of all studied cytokines was found. At the same time, the level of the studied cytokines is directly proportional to the intensity and duration of the pain syndrome, the higher and longer the intensity of pain, the higher the increase in the level of IL-1 β , which has statistical significance within - $P < 0.05$. (Table 1).

Cytokines in angina pectoris (M \pm m)

Indicators	Control group n=20	AC n=41	TC+AG, n=40
IL-1 pg/ml	13,3 \pm 0,21	28,2 \pm 0,46*	33,7 \pm 0,33*
IL-6, pg/ml	11,7 \pm 0,46	17,8 \pm 0,68*	21,9 \pm 0,59**
IL-10, pg/ml	22,4 \pm 1,33	43,4 \pm 1,3	64,5 \pm 1,33
TNF- α , pg/ml	26,4 \pm 0,76	49.9 \pm 1,33**	28,2 \pm 1,33

Note: * - differences relative to the control group data are significant (* - $P < 0.05$, ** - $P < 0.01$)

In the control group, the level of IL-1 β was 13.3 \pm 0.21pg/ml. In patients with TS and hypertension of the 2nd degree, its increase was revealed by 2.5 times - up to 33.7 \pm 0.33pg/ml ($P < 0.05$) relative to the control indicator. This tendency to increase the level of cytokines was noted when studying the level of IL-6 and IL-10 in the blood of patients with angina pectoris.

The study of the TNF- α level showed its increase by 1.89 times at AS -up to 49.9 \pm 1.33 pg/ml, against the control - 26.4 \pm 0.76 pg/ml ($P < 0.05$). And in TS with AH, the level of TNF- α - was at the level of control values -28.2 \pm 1.33 pg/ml.

Conclusion: the obtained result shows the relationship between the synthesis of pro-inflammatory cytokines and changes in lipid and carbohydrate metabolism in patients with TS and hypertension, which indicates the state of dysmetabolism and is of great importance in the development of preventive measures in this area. At the same time, in patients with TS and AH, the immune response is aimed at inducing effector cells, maintaining homeostasis.

The established facts open up promising directions for the prevention of complications of ACS, the transition of subclinical lesions of internal organs to coronary heart disease and multiple organ failure.

References:

1. Ikromovna I. F., Jumatovich J. U., Elmuradovich I. G. Influence of the harmful factors of manufacture of synthetic detergents and cleaners on the clinical-functional parameters of the oral cavities in the workers //European science review. – 2014. – №. 9-10. – С. 31-32.
2. Ибрагимова Ф. И., Жумаева А. А., Ражабова Д. Б. Влияние неблагоприятных факторов условий труда в производстве синтетических моющих и чистящих средств на

- состояние тканей пародонта у рабочих //Наука молодых-Eruditio Juvenium. – 2015. – №. 1. – С. 31-34.
3. Ikromovna I. F. Prevalence and character of the oral cavity mucosa in the workers of the manufacture of the synthetic detergents //European science review. – 2016. – №. 3-4. – С. 178-179.
4. Ибрагимова Ф. И., Замонова Г. Ш. Влияние вредных факторов производства на клинико-функциональные показатели полости рта рабочих //Символ науки. – 2016. – №. 8-1. – С. 181-182.
5. Ibragimova F. I., Idiev G. E. The state of health of workers in the production of synthetic detergents and cleaning products." Problems of Biology and Medicine //International Scientific Journal.-Samarkand. – 2012. – №. 1. – С. 68.
6. Ибрагимова Ф. И., Жуматов У. Ж. Поражения слизистой оболочки полости рта у работающих в производстве синтетических моющих и чистящих средств //Молодежный инновационный вестник. – 2016. – Т. 5. – №. 1. – С. 165-166.
7. Ибрагимова Ф. И., Замонова Г. Ш. ОЦЕНКА НЕКОТОРЫХ ФУНКЦИОНАЛЬНЫХ ПОКАЗАТЕЛЕЙ ПОЛОСТИ РТА У РАБОЧИХ ПРОИЗВОДСТВА СЫРЬЕВЫХ КОМПОНЕНТОВ ДЛЯ СИНТЕТИЧЕСКИХ МОЮЩИХ СРЕДСТВ //Молодежный инновационный вестник. – 2016. – Т. 5. – №. 1. – С. 163-165.
8. Ибрагимова Ф. И., Замонова Г. Ш. Влияние вредных факторов производства на клинико-функциональные показатели полости рта рабочих //Символ науки. – 2016. – №. 8-1. – С. 181-182.
9. Ибрагимова Ф. И., Идиев Г. Э. Действие гипохлорита натрия (ингредиента синтетических моющих средств) на активность окислительно-восстановительных ферментов, и её коррекция введением растительных препаратов в эксперименте //Проблемы биологии и медицины-Самарканд. – 2017. – Т. 4. – С. 98.
10. Idiyevna S. G. Discussion of results of personal studies in the use ofmil therapy in the treatment of trauma to the oral mucosA //European Journal of Molecular medicineVolume. – Т. 2.
11. Idiyevna S. G. THE EFFECTIVENESS OF THE USE OF MAGNETIC-IRRED-LASER THERAPY IN TRAUMATIC INJURIES OF ORAL TISSUES IN PRESCHOOL CHILDREN //Academic leadership. ISSN. – Т. 15337812.
12. Sharipova G. I. Light and laser radiation in medicine //European journal of modern medicine and practice. – 2022. – Т. 2. – №. 1. – С. 36-41.
13. Idievna S. G. THE EFFECT OF DENTAL TREATMENT-PROFILACTICS ON THE CONDITION OF ORAL CAVITY ORGANS IN CHILDREN WITH TRAUMATIC STOMATITIS //Tibbiyotdayangikun» scientific-abstract, cultural and educational journal.-Bukhara. – 2022. – Т. 5. – №. 43. – С. 103-106.
14. Idievna S. G. CHANGES IN THE CONTENT OF TRACE ELEMENTS IN THE SALIVA OF PATIENTS IN THE TREATMENT OF PATIENTS WITH TRAUMATIC STOMATITIS WITH FLAVONOID-BASED DRUGS //Journal of research in health science. – Т. 6. – С. 23-26.